

SIX-MEMBERED RING SYSTEMS: WITH O AND/OR S ATOMS

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Abstract. A large variety of publications involving O- and S-6-membered ring systems have appeared in 2018. The importance of these heterocyclic compounds is highlighted by the large number of publications on the total synthesis of natural oxygen derivatives and of other communications dedicated to natural and synthetic derivatives. Reviews on the ruthenium-catalyzed synthesis of various O-6-membered heterocycles (1), the enantioselective syntheses of 3,4-dihydropyran derivatives (2), and strategies for the synthesis of coumarins (3) have appeared. The synthesis of natural pyran-2-ones and pyran-4-ones starting from alkynes and promoted by gold complexes (4) and cyclization strategies of substituted alkynyl acids and esters to afford pyran-2-one and isocoumarin derivatives have been detailed in minireviews. The synthesis of various O-6-membered derivatives was also achieved through ultrasound irradiation (5) and using 4-hydroxy-6-methylpyran-2-one as a building block in multicomponent reactions (6).

Keywords: Gold(I)-catalyzed, aromatic substitution, 2-hydroxyaryl, 3-Alkylidene-2H-1,2-oxazines, 3-nitro-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran-5-carbonitriles, 3-

spiroxindole indolo[2,3-b]-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrans, Cyclization, dichloromethane, triethylamine, 4-hydroxycoumarin in refluxing ethanol.

Introduction.

Recent advances in the asymmetric synthesis of pyrans and chromenes (7), the chemistry of 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene for the synthesis of benzo- chromene, benzoxanthene, and benzodioxine derivatives (8), and the synthesis of flavones (9) have been discussed. The potent synthetic application of Diels-Alder reactions involving o-quinodimethanes, aza-o-quinone methides, and o-quinone methides in the total synthesis of natural products (10) and in asymmetric multicomponent reactions for the preparation of spiroxindolinone tetrahydropyran-2-ones and 2H-chromenes (11) were also overviewed.

Discussions on specific reactions such as C-H activation for the synthesis of (iso) chromans (12); ring closing metathesis (RCM) combined with enzymatic kinetic resolution applied in the synthesis of the enantiomerically pure (6R)-phenyl- 5,6-dihydro-2H-pyran-2-ones; radical reactions of aryl alkynoates for the synthesis of coumarins soft-enolization Baker Venkataraman rearrangement for the total synthesis of dichromones and related 2-substituted chromones (13); anion relay chemistry strategy for the total synthesis of

tetrahydropyran-containing mandelalides A and L (14); titanium(III)- mediated reductive epoxide opening-cyclization for the construction of the cyclopenta[d]tetrahydropyran-2-one skeleton in a few synthetic derivatives (15) and also in the total syntheses of iridomyrmecin, isoiridomyrmecin, 7- epi-boschnialactone, teucrum lactone, and dolichodial ; and pericyclic cascade reactions in the biosynthesis of natural isochromene-type derivative leporine C were accomplished.

The first synthesis of O-doped zig-zag molecular graphenes through oxidative C-C and C-O bond formations and starting from 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene has been reported (16).

The importance of specific reagents, namely, triethylamine as organocatalyst in the

synthesis of pyran-, chromene-, coumarin-, and xanthene-type compounds, and chiral hypervalent iodine reagents for the synthesis of dihydroisocoumarins have been disclosed.

Chemoenzymatic total synthesis of natural 5,6-dihydro-2H-pyran-2-ones cryptocaryalactone derivatives (17) was disclosed.

The convergent synthesis of sorangicin A involves ring closing metathesis (RCM) for the formation of the tetrahydropyran ring and a 5-endo iodoetherification to construct the dioxabicyclo[3.2.1]octane subunit (18). Enantiospecific total synthesis of cryptopyranmoscatone B2 is accomplished via FeCl₃-catalyzed cyclization of an allyl alcohol to form the tetrahydropyran core and RCM reactions to afford the 5,6-dihydropyran-2-one moiety. In the total synthesis of projerangolide and jerangolide E, the tetrahydropyran rings were obtained by intramolecular oxa-Michael addition while the 5,6-dihydropyran-2-one units were formed by lactonization under weakly basic conditions (19).

The synthesis of tetrahydropyran-containing C-1eC-8 and C-9eC-19 fragments of phorboxazole A (20) and the synthesis and stereochemical revision of C-31eC-67 fragment of amphidinol 3 was disclosed.

Some heterocyclic-fused chromans were synthesized and their potential application as blue-fluorescent probes was studied and a novel 2,10-bis-styryl-1-benzopyrylium dye revealed extended p-conjugation, which is very important for application as a photosensitizer in dye-sensitive solar cells.

Herein, we provide a personal overview of the most relevant transformations on O- and S-6-membered heterocycles, published in 2018.

Results and discussion.

Gold(I)-catalyzed intramolecular cyclization through electrophilic aromatic substitution of 4-propargyloxyisoxazoles led to isoxazole-fused 2H-pyrans (21). The synthesis of benzo[4,5]thieno[3,2-b]pyrans was accomplished through a phosphinecatalyzed [4+2] annulation reaction of 2-alkylidenebenzothiophen-3(2H)-

ones with *g*-benzyl allenates (22). The reaction of thioaurone-type compounds with crotonate-derived sulfur ylides is substrate-controlled: (a) compounds bearing an ester or acyl group at the α -position of the 2-alkylidene substituent undergo a [4 2] annulation reaction in the presence of cesium carbonate to afford benzo[4,5]thieno[3,2-*b*]

pyrans; (b) compounds bearing an aryl group undergo a new [4 2] annulation reaction in the presence of *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA) with sulfide incorporation to give 2-[(methylthio)methyl]benzo[4,5]thieno[3,2-*b*]-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrans; and finally (c) compounds bearing a 2-hydroxyaryl group, underwent vinylcyclopropane rearrangement domino reaction to provide 3-(3-hydroxybenzo[*b*]thiophen-2-yl)-2H-chromene derivatives (Scheme 1) (23).

Scheme 1

3-Alkylidene-2H-1,2-oxazines, obtained from regioselective [4 2] cycloaddition reactions of alkenylallenes with nitrosoarenes in THF, undergo triflic acid-promoted rearrangement to form pyran-3(6H)-imines. Under visible-light irradiation, trifluoromethylative intramolecular cyclization of 5-arylpent-4-yn-1-ols carried out in the presence of $\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_3$, Umemoto reagent, and lithium carbonate in acetonitrile provides 6-aryl-5-trifluoromethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrans (24). Highly substituted 3-nitro-3,4-

dihydro-2H-pyran-5-carbonitriles are enantioselectively obtained

from a formal oxa-[4 2] annulation reaction of nitroethylene with α -cyano- α,β -unsaturated aryl ketones in the presence of a dipeptide-based phosphine catalyst **1** and 2-methoxybenzoic acid ([Scheme 2](#)) ([25](#)).

Scheme 2

Various pentacyclic 3-spiroxindole indolo[2,3-*b*]-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrans result from one-pot asymmetric aldol/chloroetherification/aromatization sequence involving the reaction of 3-(indol-3-ylmethyl)oxindoles with paraformaldehyde in the presence of a chiral tertiary amine catalyst in DCE, followed by the addition of *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS) in the presence of 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) ([26](#)).

Cyclization reactions of allenic alcohols with aldehydes in dichloromethane at 0 °C promoted by bismuth(III) trifluoromethanesulfonate leads to 3,6-dihydro-2H-pyrans while using trimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate (TMSOTf) at 45 °C provides hexahydropyrano[4,3-*b*]pyrans ([27](#)). Some 5,6-dihydro-2H-pyrans are obtained from enyne metathesis using ruthenium dihydride complexes as catalysts ([28](#)). A series of indolo[2,3-*c*]-5,6-dihydro-2H-pyrans were prepared via intramolecular oxa-Pictet-Spengler reactions of 3-(2-vinyloxyethan-1-yl)indoles, under dual catalysis of urea and a chiral phosphoric acid in toluene at 40 °C. Further derivatives arise from trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)-catalyzed oxa-Pictet-Spengler reactions of 3-(2-hydroxyethan-1-yl)indoles with acetals, prepared in situ from aldehydes and

trimethyl orthoformate, in dichloromethane at room temperature (Scheme 3).

Several 4-spiroindolin-2-one 2-amino-4H-pyran-3-carbonitriles were synthesized through the reaction of isatylidenes with dialkyl acetone-1,3-dicarboxylates in the presence of triethylamine using ethanol as solvent (29).

One-pot cascade heterocyclization reactions of 2-(3-oxo-1,3-diarylpropyl)malono-nitriles promoted by triphosgene and triphenylphosphine oxide lead to 2,4-dichloropyrimidino[4,5-b]-4,6-diaryl-4H-pyrans. A series of 1,3-disubstituted pyrazolo[5,4-b]pyrans were synthesized via asymmetric [3+3]annulation reactions of 1,3-disubstituted 1H-pyrazol-5(4H)-ones with ethynyl benzox-azinanones (Scheme 4), or 3-trimethylsilylpropargylic acetates (30) mediated by copper complexes of chiral P,P-bidentate or P,N,N-tridentate ligands, respectively; or with 3-(2-arylethynyl)-3-alken-2-ones promoted by a tertiary amine squaramide catalyst. The synthesis of 2-amino-1,3-disubstituted pyrazolo[5,4-b]pyran-3-carbonitriles is accomplished via one-pot, three-component reaction of aromatic aldehydes with malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one catalyzed by recyclable $Zn(ANA)_2Cl_2$ (ANA 2-- aminonicotinaldehyde) in water and by sodium fluoride under ultrasonic irradiation (31). Four-component reactions of benzyl halides with malononitrile/ethyl cyanoacetate, diethyl acetylenedicarboxylate/ethyl acetoacetate and hydrazine hydrate promoted by N-methylmorpholine N-oxide and silver oxide in refluxing ethanol provides 2-amino-3-substituted pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyran-3-carbonitrile/carboxylates.

A chiral squaramide catalyzes Michael addition/cyclization tandem reaction of dimedone with isatylidenemalononitriles to afford 4-spiroxindolin-2-one cyclohexanone-fused 2-amino-4H-pyran-3-carbonitriles in excellent yields and with excellent enantioselectivity. A wide range of 4-spiroxindolin-2-one coumarin-fused 3-substituted 2-amino-4H-pyrans were synthesized via one-pot, three-component reactions of isatins with 4-hydroxycoumarin and active methylene compounds in *g*-valerolactone as a green reaction media and of Nalkyl-1-(methylthio)-2-nitroethenamine, derived from the addition of various amines to nitroketene dithioacetal, with isatin derivatives and 4-hydroxycoumarin in refluxing ethanol (32). One-pot, four-component reactions of isatins with 4-methyleneoxetan-2-one, hydrazine hydrate, and malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate in the presence of iodine in ethanol at room temperature provides 4-spiroxindolin 2-one pyrazole-fused 2-amino-4H-pyran derivatives (Scheme 5).

Conclusion.

The importance of these heterocyclic compounds is highlighted by the large number of publications on the total synthesis of natural oxygen derivatives and of other communications dedicated to natural and synthetic derivatives. Reviews on the ruthenium-catalyzed synthesis of various O-6-membered heterocycles, the enantioselective syntheses of 3,4-dihydropyran derivatives, and strategies for the synthesis of coumarins have appeared. The synthesis of natural pyran-2-ones and pyran-4-ones starting from alkynes and promoted by gold complexes and cyclization strategies of substituted alkynyl acids and esters to afford pyran-2-one and isocoumarin derivatives have been detailed in minireviews. The synthesis of various O-6-membered derivatives was also achieved through ultrasound irradiation and using 4-hydroxy-6-methylpyran-2-one as a building block in multicomponent reactions.

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